

Predicting historical oxygen deficiency areas in the western Baltic Sea: A multi-model approach

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ABSTRACT

The oceans are under increasing pressure from human activities. In order to manage these, target values describing good environmental status are often determined based on a historical state without significant human impact. Deoxygenation is one of the most harmful indirect effects of human induced coastal eutrophication, and it is important to quantify oxygen deficiency in bottom waters. However, historical oxygen measurements are scarce and models are needed for integrating these point observations. We used a combined approach integrating the results of three models – a statistical, mechanistic, and machine learning model – to estimate the area affected by oxygen deficiency from 1949 to 1969 in the western Baltic Sea. Hypoxia (oxygen <2 mg/l) was rare with <1 % to 3 % of the near-bottom area being predicted as hypoxic with a high to low confidence, respectively. But all sub-basins exhibited oxygen deficiency (oxygen <6 mg/l) with a share of 11 % (high confidence) to 37 % (low confidence) of the whole area. The statistical model predicted the smallest areas of oxygen deficiency, while the mechanistic model predicted the largest. A major uncertainty identified relates to the estimation of oxygen concentrations in the bottom boundary layer, as it is considered differently by our three methods and observational data for model tuning in this layer are lacking. Our multi-model approach provides an estimate of the historical extent of oxygen deficiency with higher confidence than any of the three approaches alone. This estimate can help to define targets for ecological indicators of oxygen deficiency.

1. Introduction

Oxygen levels serve as an essential indicator of marine ecosystems health, as prolonged and sustained periods of oxygen deficiency are associated with negative effects such as altered biogeochemical cycles, declining habitats, mass mortality events, and a loss of biodiversity (Breitburg et al., 2018; Diaz and Rosenberg, 2008; Sampaio et al., 2021; Vaquer-Sunyer and Duarte, 2008). Enclosed seas, such as the Baltic Sea, are particularly prone to oxygen deficiency (here defined as oxygen concentrations <6 mg/l) due to a restricted ventilation of high-density saline bottom waters with low-density surface waters as well as a long water residence time, in case of the Baltic Sea of about 30 years (Snoeijs-Leijonmalm et al., 2017). Simultaneously, the Baltic Sea is sensitive to excess anthropogenic nutrient inputs from the atmosphere and rivers that have led to eutrophication (Murray et al., 2019; Savchuk, 2018) with oxygen deficiency as one of its most detrimental symptoms

(Carstensen and Conley, 2019). Likewise to global trends (Breitburg et al., 2018), oxygen deficiency has been increasingly observed in coastal areas in the Baltic Sea in recent decades (Conley et al., 2011) and future climate change may further promote deoxygenation in the Baltic Sea (Gröger et al., 2024; Meier et al., 2018; Safonova et al., 2024).

Thus, oxygen is already included as an indicator for “good environmental status” within the European Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD, 2008/56/EC; European Commission, 2008), the trends of which must be assessed and for which mitigation measures need to be implemented if targets are compromised. The derivation of targets constitutes a critical step, as the comparison of assessment results to the target delineates whether good environmental status has been achieved or not. In order to define target values that provide a threshold for a separation of a desirable and undesirable status, it is necessary to consider the situation in the past, prior to any significant human influence. In the context of the Baltic Sea the period before 1940 has been

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characterized as pre-eutrophication period (HELCOM, 2013), whereas the period prior to 1970 is often considered having a good, up to high ecological status (Carstensen and Henriksen, 2009; Schories et al., 2009). For example, the extent of permanent hypoxia (oxygen <2 mg/l) in the deep basins of the Baltic Sea was limited to a small area and volume prior to 1950, with notable changes observed in subsequent years (HELCOM, 2013).

A major limitation in assessing the historical situation is that historical data are few and scattered in time and space, which makes it difficult to produce reliable area estimates for this period, especially for the more dynamic seasonal oxygen deficiency in shallow waters. However, to develop a meaningful indicator for seasonal oxygen deficiency, it is crucial to consider the spatial context.

Spatial estimates of hypoxia or oxygen deficiency are often based on spatial inter- and/or extrapolation of observations (Conley et al., 2002; Jutras et al., 2023) and are utilized for example to provide long-term monitoring products of hypoxic areas in the Baltic Sea (Feistel et al., 2016; Hansson and Viktorsson, 2024). These methods are suitable with spatio-temporal comprehensive monitoring, but unsuitable for comparing years or periods when underlying data vary broadly in time and space (Feistel et al., 2016). Mechanistic models on the other hand provide a powerful tool for three-dimensional visualization of oxygen deficiency in an area (Fennel et al., 2019), but they require validation against observational data. The limited availability of historical data may explain the few mechanistic modelling studies on historical oxygen deficiency prior to the 1970s. Statistical (regression) models are mainly used to find time-dependent relationships between the extent of oxygen deficiency and various parameters such as riverine nutrient discharge (Forrest et al., 2012), physical (Herrera-Becerril et al., 2022) or geomorphological parameters (Virtanen et al., 2019). However, regression models are typically not employed for localizing oxygen deficiency in an area but incorporating the spatial dimension they can also be used for this purpose.

As most of the current methods for estimating area extents are developed for modern monitoring programs with regular and frequent monitoring, they cannot be applied to the sparse historical data. While several studies and reports have addressed the long-term development of permanent hypoxia in the Baltic Proper (Almroth-Rosell et al., 2021; Carstensen et al., 2014) few have estimated the areal extent of seasonal oxygen deficiency in the western Baltic Sea prior to 1970. Piehl et al. (2023) analyzed the temporal development since 1950 in the western Baltic Sea using a mechanistic model. The area estimates derived from this study were based on annual averages of the near-bottom oxygen concentration including months without oxygen deficiency; consequently, they are not able to reliably represent the maximum extent of the seasonal oxygen deficiency. Another study utilized different geo-statistical mapping approaches to provide historic area estimates of oxygen deficiency in the same area from 1950 onwards (Friedland et al., 2023). The authors used annual minimum near-bottom oxygen concentrations from July to November to estimate the spatial extent of oxygen deficiency. However, it was noted that the proceeding might lead to an overestimation of oxygen deficiency areas if the annual minima do not occur at the same time. The discrepancies between the results of the two studies can be attributed to the individual methods used but also to the different analysis strategies (utilized metrics, thresholds, time-periods). Moreover, the Belt Sea was not included in any of the studies, despite also being a highly vulnerable area for seasonal oxygen deficiency (Conley et al., 2011).

As previous studies on the extent of oxygen deficiency in the Baltic Sea either did not cover the same areas, months, decades and thresholds or used different data aggregation methods, an approach needs to be developed to estimate the historical extent of seasonal hypoxia and oxygen deficiency over a period with relatively few and scattered observations. Since the application and assessment of multiple models can have many advantages over assessing the results of a single model, ideally a set of suitable models should be used for this purpose. The

underlying principle is that the results will be more robust and reliable if multiple lines of models, data sets, or algorithms align and corroborate each other (Weller et al., 2013). Furthermore, the conceptual understanding of the system can be enhanced, and the most significant uncertainties can be identified (Scavia et al., 2017). Finally, information from multiple models can provide more robust estimations with realistic uncertainty ranges which is critical to rational decision-making.

In order to estimate the historical area extent of oxygen deficiency in the western Baltic Sea and to overcome the limitations of a single model, we employed three different models with the same analysis strategy: I) a statistical non-parametric generalized additive model (GAM), II) a coupled hydrodynamic-biogeochemical model (MOM-ERGOM), and III) a machine learning model (Gaussian Process Boosting).

Our objective is to provide a reliable estimate of the historical extent of near-bottom oxygen deficiency, along with a confidence estimate. Specifically, we aim to answer the following questions: To what extent was the western Baltic Sea affected by near-bottom oxygen deficiency in the past? What is the main source of uncertainty in the estimation of oxygen deficiency areas by our approach? What are the resulting implications for indicator development?

2. Material and methods

2.1. Study area

The Baltic Sea is a semi-enclosed brackish sea that has limited water exchange with the ocean through the connection of the Kattegat with the North Sea. The western Baltic Sea, here defined as the area from the Kattegat to the Arkona Basin, is a transition zone between the marine areas bordering the North Sea and the more brackish parts of the Baltic Sea east of the Arkona Basin (Fig. 1). The region can be characterized as a large estuarine system in which outflowing surface water from the Baltic is separated from saline inflowing bottom water (Hansen and Bendtsen, 2013). A pronounced horizontal and vertical salinity gradient characterizes the ecosystem and determines habitat and species distribution but also vertical mixing of water (Snoeijs-Leijonmalm et al., 2017). The (western) Baltic Sea is of high economic value, creating jobs and incomes in, e.g., the fisheries, tourism, shipping, and renewable energy sectors (HELCOM, 2023).

Besides a permanent halocline, a thermocline develops in spring. The temperature difference between the surface and the deep water layer as well as the depth of the thermocline, reach their maximum in August. The halocline located between 15 and 20 m in the western Baltic Sea (besides the Arkona Basin where it is located at about 20–35 m depth; Lass and Mohrholz, 2003) coincides with the summer thermocline between 10 and 15 m (Snoeijs-Leijonmalm et al., 2017). Due to the cooling and stormier weather in autumn, mixing increases, resulting in the erosion of the thermocline. The hydrographic conditions in the Kattegat are highly affected by the exchange of water between the North Sea and the Baltic Sea. In addition to creating a distinct salinity stratification, this process also gives rise to highly dynamic surface waters. The dynamics through the Sound and the Belt Sea are highly variable, with fluctuations in water flow rates up to 100,000 m³/s in both directions (Snoeijs-Leijonmalm et al., 2017). The 18 to 24 km wide Fehmarn Belt, together with the Great Belt, is the most important passage for water exchange between the Kattegat (i.e., the North Sea) and the Baltic Sea basins (Fig. 1). The Bay of Mecklenburg is slightly shallower (average depth 16 m) than the Kiel Bay (average depth 17 m), but substantially shallower than the Arkona Basin with an average depth of 25 m (Fig. 1). The initial entry of bottom waters originating from the North Sea into the Arkona Basin occurs via the Sound where it needs to pass the 8 m shallow Drogden Sill (Snoeijs-Leijonmalm et al., 2017). Somewhat delayed, the inflowing saltwater reaches the Arkona Basin also through the Kadet trench. The Drogden Sill and the Darss Sill are the shallowest natural barriers for water exchange between the western Baltic Sea and the neighboring north-eastern basins. Here the Baltic Sea gradient

Fig. 1. (a) Location of our study area the western Baltic Sea (red rectangle) and (b) bathymetric map and key characteristics of the investigated HELCOM sub-basins (red). DRS: Drogden sill, FB: Fehmarn Belt, KT: Kadet trench, DAS: Darss sill. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

changes from strongly fluctuating brackish water conditions to relatively stable conditions with low salinities. Thus, the Arkona Basin is regarded as an area with relatively stable low-salinity conditions, with a much more constant surface water salinity (Snoeijs-Leijonmalm et al., 2017).

2.2. Observational data

For the current study observations deeper than 10 m in the months from August to October in the period from 1949 to 1969 (Fig. 2) were obtained from the national marine monitoring database at Aarhus University. These data originate from ICES, with coastal data obtained from national sources (Leibniz Institute for Baltic Sea Research Warnemünde (IOW), Danish EPA (Miljøstyrelsen), and Swedish Meteorological

Fig. 2. Number of observations across years, months, and HELCOM sub-basins in the western Baltic Sea. Total number of observations per sub-basin in brackets.

and Hydrological Institute (SMHI)).

We used the oxygen concentrations as response variable for the GAM model as well as the machine-learning model. The GAM model further included salinity, temperature, depth, month, and location (coordinates) from the obtained dataset as explanatory variables.

We averaged the measured 1140 observations (Fig. 2) to monthly averages for validation with the ERGOM model results (1032 observations). To compare observed and predicted values, the model data were matched up with observations in time and space. For comparison with the deepest model layer only measurements within a water column up to 5 m above the seafloor were included (966 observations).

Before 1960 only the Belt Sea and Kiel Bay had a higher number of observations and afterwards fewer, whereas for all other sub-basins the reverse was true (Fig. 2). In contrast to the basins closer to the North Sea (upper panel Fig. 2), the number of measurements in September were relatively low in the Kiel Bay, Bay of Mecklenburg and Arkona Basin compared to the other months. The uneven temporal distribution of observations should be taken into account, as oxygen deficiency in the open western Baltic Sea usually reaches its maximum extent in September, which means that oxygen deficiency, in sub-basins with fewer measurements in September, may be underestimated. Moreover, the fewer observations in the Kattegat and the Bay of Mecklenburg (relative to their areal extent) should be considered. Few observations are generally a limitation for modelling and model validation, since noise in the data has a higher impact on both model results and skill metrics.

2.3. Modelling approaches

For evaluating the historic situation of hypoxia and oxygen deficiency three oxygen thresholds were considered. Hypoxia is defined as oxygen concentrations of <2 mg/l, while strong and regular oxygen deficiency are defined as oxygen concentrations of <4 mg/l and <6 mg/l, respectively. For our calculations of the historical oxygen deficiency areas, we averaged the areal estimates from August to October in the period 1949–1969, representing those months with the largest extent of oxygen deficiency. The inclusion of multiple years was necessary to obtain sufficient measurements for the modelling, but also corresponds to current management practice in which several years are considered within an assessment.

Spatial maps were prepared using the software R utilizing the coordinate reference system UTM 32N (EPSG:25832) as basis for calculating areas below the different oxygen thresholds. For the sub-basin area calculations, we used the HELCOM classification scheme of level-2 units, which includes both, coastal waters and parts of the open sea.

2.3.1. Statistical model (GAM)

Oxygen concentrations in bottom waters can be described using the water mass properties (salinity S and temperature T) and applying a time (categorical factor $month_i$ for describing differences between the three months) and location-specific (depth z and coordinates x, y in UTM 32N) modification to account for the oxygen consumption. A non-parametric Generalized Additive Model (GAM) was chosen to predict oxygen concentrations near the bottom (DO_{bottom}).

$$DO_{bottom} = month_i + s(z) + s(S) + s(T) + s_2(x, y) + e \quad (1)$$

The three spline functions for depth, salinity, and temperature describe a non-parametric general relationship between oxygen and these three variables. The curvature of these relationships was restricted to 3 degrees of freedom. Importantly, $s(z)$ describes the decrease of oxygen with depth and therefore accounts for that the deepest oxygen measurement in the profile may not always represent the bottom oxygen concentration. The thin-plate spline function ($s_2(x, y)$) describes a location-specific variation, in two dimensions restricted to 20 degrees of freedom, in addition to the variation explained by salinity, temperature, and depth. The model describes the mean oxygen concentration and

therefore considers the variability of oxygen concentrations among years as random variation, i.e. the model predicts the mean oxygen concentration across all years with data, and not any specific year.

For predicting DO_{bottom} across the entire area from the GAM model (Eq. (1)), spatial distributions of salinity (S) and temperature (T) were needed. These were produced from the following GAM model, having a similar but reduced form:

$$S/T = month_i + s(z) + s_2(x, y) + e \quad (2)$$

where $month_i$ is a categorical factor describing the difference in salinity and temperature between months (August–October), $s(z)$ describes how S/T changes with depth and $s_2(x, y)$ is a thin-plate spline describing spatial variations unaccounted by $s(z)$. Maps of bottom salinity and temperature were compiled from this model to predict bottom oxygen concentrations with the GAM model. Depth is an important predictor of salinity and temperature, since salinity increases and temperature in summer decreases with depth. In addition to depth there is also a pronounced spatial gradient with lower salinity and temperature from the Kattegat towards the Arkona Basin.

2.3.2. Mechanistic model (ERGOM)

The mechanistic model results for the western Baltic Sea (Fig. 1) originate from model simulations of the whole Baltic Sea with the integrated biogeochemical model ERGOM (www.ergom.net) which is coupled to a 3D hydrodynamic model (MOM; Neumann et al., 2021). The three nutrients dissolved in water, ammonium, nitrate, and phosphate, are the basis for primary production that is realized by three functional phytoplankton groups (i.e., large and small cells, cyanobacteria; Neumann et al., 2022). Grazing pressure on the phytoplankton is applied via a dynamically developing bulk zooplankton variable. Dead organic material is reflected by a detritus state variable. Phytoplankton and detritus can sink and accumulate in a sediment layer, whereby part of the detritus is mineralized back into dissolved ammonium and phosphate during the sinking process. The portion that reaches the seafloor accumulates and is either buried permanently, mineralized, or resuspended when the velocity of near-bottom currents is sufficiently high. Under oxic conditions, a proportion of the mineralized phosphate is bound by iron oxides and retained as particles within the sediment. Erosion events have the potential to resuspend these particles, and currents facilitate their transport towards particle accumulation areas. When conditions become anoxic, iron-oxid becomes reduced and phosphate is released back to the water column. Oxygen is produced by primary production and consumed due to all other processes, e.g., metabolism and mineralization. The development of oxygen is additionally linked to biogeochemical processes through the application of stoichiometric ratios. The model is described in detail by Neumann et al. (2022).

The physical part of the model is based on the circulation model MOM (version 5.1; (Griffies et al., 2004; Griffies, 2012) which was adapted to the Baltic Sea taking into account an open boundary condition to the North Sea and the freshwater input by rivers. The MOM model is further enhanced with the incorporation of a sea ice model (Winton, 2000). The horizontal resolution of the model grid is one nautical mile. Vertically the model is resolved into 152 layers, with a layer thickness of 0.5 m at the surface and gradually increasing with depth up to two meters. Atmospheric forcing is based on a dynamical downscaling provided by the coastDat data set with a grid resolution of about 25×25 km (Weisse et al., 2009; Geyer and Rockel, 2013). Nutrient loads to the Baltic Sea due to riverine discharge were taken from HELCOM assessments (e.g., HELCOM, 2021; https://nest.su.se/helcom_plc/) and atmospheric deposition of nitrogen inputs from EMEP (Gauss et al., 2021; <https://emep.int/publ/helcom/2018/index.html>).

We extracted the monthly available historic oxygen concentrations from the deepest model layer for August, September, and October from 1949 to 1969. Following this, we converted the unit from mol/kg to mg/

l, and the mean of all extracted values within the specified period for each model cell was calculated.

2.3.3. Machine learning model (GPBoost)

The machine learning model complements both the GAM model, which relies solely on available measurements, and the ERGOM model by providing a hybrid approach that incorporates both, near-bottom oxygen measurements and modelled data. Specifically, we employed mixed-effects machine learning with GPBoost (Gaussian Process Boosting). Gradient boosting is the stepwise construction of models using decision trees where each new model attempts to correct the errors of the previous one. This is combined with the spatial correlation modelling capabilities of Gaussian processes and grouped random effect models. This allows for the incorporation of a spatial random effect modelled by a Gaussian Process (Sigrist, 2022) and in our case to introduce the temporal parameters *month* and *year* as grouped random effects. This is particularly useful, as certain month/year combinations have very few observations (Fig. 2).

For the prediction of near-bottom oxygen concentrations only measurements within a water column up to 5 m above the seafloor were utilized. The physico-chemical properties which were included as predictor variables were obtained from the mechanistic model ERGOM, the bathymetry was taken from the EMODnet database (<https://portal.emodnet-bathymetry.eu/>). Physico-chemical properties known to influence oxygen concentration at the seafloor were used as predictor variables, i. e., bathymetric depth, bottom temperature and salinity, depth of the mixed layer, the thickness of the water layer below the mixed layer, and density difference between surface and bottom water. In addition, year and month were included as grouped random effects. The model was specified with a Gaussian likelihood and an exponential covariance function.

A grid search was performed to identify the best set of hyperparameters among the following values: learning rate $\in \{0.1, 0.05, 0.03\}$, minimum samples per leaf $\in \{15, 20, 25\}$, maximum tree depth $\in \{7, 8, 9\}$, maximum number of leaves $\in \{15, 20, 25\}$, and number of boosting iterations $\in \{80, 90, 110\}$. Model performance was evaluated based on the RMSE and Coefficient of Determination (R^2) that were obtained from a 10-fold cross-validation according to Linnenbrink et al. (2024). Data preparation, modelling, and model evaluation were performed using R (version 4.4.0). R-packages which implement the GPBoost algorithm (Sigrist, 2022) and that aid the application of a suitable cross-validation scheme (Meyer et al., 2024) were used. The resulting model was applied to predict the spatial distribution of oxygen for each month and year combination individually, and averaged across months and years to produce the final average prediction.

SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) values (Lundberg and Lee, 2017) were used to interpret the GPBoost predictions and to understand the influence of physico-chemical covariates on bottom oxygen concentrations (i.e., the fixed effects function). SHAP values indicate the impact of the covariate on the model output in terms of their contribution to the prediction, with a higher value indicating a higher contribution. This allows for the identification of feature importance and helps to interpret how each covariate affects bottom oxygen concentration.

3. Results

3.1. Modelling approaches

3.1.1. Statistical model (GAM)

The GAM model explained 65 % of the variation in historical oxygen concentration and all effects were significant ($P < 0.05$). Location was the most important descriptor of oxygen concentration, followed by salinity, temperature, and depth. The month factor showed that oxygen concentrations were lowest in September, followed by August and then October (Fig. S2a). In fact, oxygen concentrations in September and

August were 0.95 and 0.45 mg/l lower, respectively, than oxygen concentrations in October.

The marginal relationship of oxygen concentrations to depth (i.e., when accounting for the other effects in the GAM model) showed a gradual decline of around 1.6 mg/l (Fig. S2b). The marginal relationship to salinity showed a marked decline from lower salinity down to about 25 and then slightly increasing oxygen concentrations with higher salinities in the Kattegat (Fig. S2c). Similarly, the marginal relationship to temperature exhibited the lowest values around 8–9 °C, around 1 mg/l lower than for the highest and lowest temperatures (Fig. S2d). Thus, the GAM model suggests that the most oxygen depleted waters are characterized by salinity around 25 and temperature around 8–9 °C. Finally, the 2-dimensional spline showed that oxygen concentrations were up to 3 mg/l lower in the southwestern parts and more than 3.5 mg/l higher in the northern Kattegat (Fig. S3). Hence, in addition to depth and physical properties of the water mass, the location could explain differences in oxygen concentrations of almost 7 mg/l.

Generally, areas <10 m could not be resolved with the statistical model as well as the relatively shallow eastern-most parts of the Arkona Basin (white areas in Fig. 3a) due to lack of measurements in this area. However, since the comparison among the approaches focuses on oxygen concentrations <6 mg/l, generally present only in deeper areas, this difference does not seriously affect our model output comparisons (Fig. 3).

The spatially projected GAM results highlighted that the southeastern most area of the Belt Sea, the adjacent northeastern area of Kiel Bay and the southernmost inner parts of the Bay of Mecklenburg are most prone to oxygen deficiency (Fig. 3a).

3.1.2. Mechanistic model (ERGOM)

Compared to the observations, ERGOM generally tends to underestimate oxygen in The Sound, Bay of Mecklenburg, and Arkona Basin (Fig. 4) within the analyzed period. On the contrary, it tends to overestimate oxygen in the Kattegat and the Kiel Bay (Fig. 4). The RMSE is generally increasing from the entrance area close to the North Sea (1.44) towards the east (3.41; Table S1).

Main differences occur in the Kadet trench and the Arkona Basin (Fig. 4). In the Arkona Basin, it should be noted that measurements are highly variable even in its central parts (Fig. S4), which may influence the skill metrics (Table S1). In general, the model appears to maintain the stratification of the water body for too long (Piehl et al., 2023).

Among the three models, ERGOM not only indicated the largest area affected by oxygen deficiency but also the lowest oxygen concentrations in the investigated area (Fig. 3, Table 1). In contrast to the GAM model, the biogeochemical model generally showed larger areas with oxygen concentrations below 6 mg/l (Fig. 3). In addition to the areas affected by oxygen deficiency identified by the GAM model, the ERGOM model identified small areas north of Funen and southeast of Zealand as well as the deeper parts of the Arkona Basin as vulnerable areas.

3.1.3. Machine-learning model (GPBoost)

The 10-fold cross-validation reports a RMSE of 1.84, a MAE of 1.44 and R^2 of 0.47. Unlike the ERGOM model, GPBoost shows no general tendency to over- or underestimate oxygen concentrations for specific areas (Fig. S5). The SHAP summary plot (Fig. 5) highlights the contribution of the covariates on the prediction of the fixed-effect term of the model. The covariates are ranked by their importance, i.e., their mean absolute contribution.

With a SHAP value of 0.45, density difference is the most important feature influencing the model output, followed by salinity, temperature, mixed layer depth (mld), thickness of water column below mixed layer depth (mld.below), and bathymetric depth (Fig. 5). Considering the range of oxygen concentrations (Fig. S4), the SHAP values, i.e., the influence of the covariates on the response, are small. Nevertheless, the GPBoost model indicates that greater density differences between bottom and surface waters (purple dots representing high density

Fig. 3. Average predicted historic (1949–1969) near-bottom oxygen concentrations (mg/l) from August to October by (a) the statistical model (GAM), (b) the mechanistic model (ERGOM), and (c) the machine-learning model (GPBoost). Depths which were not considered in the GAM approach are shown as white areas in the map.

Fig. 4. Calculated average differences of measured historic (1949–1969) near-bottom oxygen concentrations (mg/l; up to five meters above seafloor) during August to October and oxygen concentrations predicted by the biogeochemical model (ERGOM) for the same period and location. Positive values (blue) indicate an overestimation and negative values an underestimation (red) of oxygen concentrations by the model. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

difference) and reduced water mixing (yellow dots representing low mixed layer depth) drive lower predicted bottom oxygen concentrations (negative shifts on the x-axis). Lower oxygen concentrations are further

associated with medium salinities (pink dots on negative scale of x-axis), while higher oxygen concentrations are associated with medium temperatures (Fig. 5).

The error term of the random effects model has a variance of 0.94, reflecting the residual variability in the response that is not explained by the fixed effects or random effects. The grouped random effects month and year show smaller variances of 0.11 and 0.45, respectively. Notably, the Gaussian Process (GP) term has a large marginal variance of 3.19, i. e., a considerable amount of spatial correlation. In the context of the overall variance in the response variable (7.2), a considerable amount of the variability in the data is thus explained by the spatial random effect.

This corroborates the findings of the GAM model, also identifying location as an important parameter for predicting oxygen concentrations. Moreover, both models showed a non-linear relationship of oxygen concentrations with salinity and temperature. In contrast to “depth” in the GAM model, “density difference” was the most important parameter after salinity and temperature in the GPBoost model. The results of the GPBoost model fall between those of the GAM and ERGOM model, reflecting the utilization of observed oxygen data in combination with spatially high resolved model parameters to predict its distribution. However, a clear difference can be seen for the Arkona Basin, where the GPBoost model showed the least areas affected by oxygen deficiency in contrast to the other two models (Fig. 3).

3.2. Areal extent of historic oxygen deficiency

For the Kattegat none of the models predicted hypoxic or oxygen deficiency areas <4 mg/l (besides <1 % predicted by ERGOM) in the investigated period from 1949 to 1969 during August to October (Table 1). The situation for the Sound area is similar for hypoxic and oxygen deficiency areas <4 mg/l with only an oxygen deficiency area of 6 % being predicted by ERGOM.

According to the GAM and GPBoost results only a small area (~ 45 and 48 km², respectively) in the Belt Sea was affected by seasonal hypoxia (<2 mg/l). In contrast, ERGOM predicted an almost 10-fold larger hypoxic area of 410 km² in the Belt Sea (Fig. 3, Table 1) which corresponds to a 4 % share of the area. For Kiel Bay (111 km²) and the Arkona Basin (613 km²) a similar share of 3 % of the area is predicted to be hypoxic, and for the Bay of Mecklenburg, as much as 16 % of the area

Table 1
Oxygen deficiency areas (August–October) and their relative proportion within each sub-basin for the different oxygen thresholds estimated by the different models.

Threshold [mg/l]	Assessment unit	Area [km ²]			Percentage [%]		
		GAM	ERGOM	GPBoost	GAM	ERGOM	GPBoost
<2	Kattegat	0	6	0	0	<1	0
	The Sound	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Belt Sea	45	410	48	<1	4	<1
	Kiel Bay	1	111	0	<1	3	0
	Bay of Mecklenburg	0	722	0	0	16	0
	Arkona basin	0	613	0	0	3	0
	Kattegat	0	22	0	0	<1	0
	The Sound	0	51	0	0	6	0
	Belt Sea	906	1212	1535	9	11	14
<4	Kiel Bay	592	661	967	16	18	27
	Bay of Mecklenburg	231	1904	877	5	41	19
	Arkona basin	0	3535	0	0	20	0
	Kattegat	6116	556	395	26	2	2
	The Sound	229	175	100	25	19	11
	Belt Sea	3412	2935	5486	32	28	52
	Kiel Bay	2441	2105	2956	68	59	82
	Bay of Mecklenburg	2273	2813	2917	49	61	63
	Arkona basin	5175	5646	1243	29	32	7

Fig. 5. SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) summary plot showing the features, their mean SHAP values on the y-axis, and the impact on the SHAP value on the response variable, i.e., near-bottom oxygen concentrations, on the x-axis. Gradient colors indicate the original value of the covariates.

is classified as hypoxic (722 km²) according to the ERGOM results. ERGOMs predictions in the Belt Sea for areas with oxygen levels <4 mg/l were between the other two models. GAM and GPBoost generally predicted the largest areas for the Belt Sea at this oxygen level (906 and 1535 km², respectively) compared to the other sub-basins (Table 1). While GPBoost predicted similarly large areas for this oxygen level for Kiel Bay and the Bay of Mecklenburg, GAM predicted significantly larger

areas for Kiel Bay and ERGOM for the Mecklenburg Bay when comparing the two basins to each other. For the Arkona Basin only ERGOM predicted an oxygen deficiency area of 20 % below 4 mg/l (Table 1).

All sub-basins exhibited areas with oxygen deficiency below 6 mg/l, with the Kiel Bay (59 % to 82 %) and the Bay of Mecklenburg (49 % to 63 %) having the highest proportions according to all three models

(Table 1). In addition, the Belt Sea (32 % to 52 %) and the Arkona Basin (29 % to 32 %) showed high area shares, whereas the GPBoost model predicted a much smaller area for the latter (7 %). For the Sound, the predictions ranged from 11 % (GPBoost) to 25 % (GAM). And while the GAM model predicted an oxygen deficiency area of 26 % at the threshold of 6 mg/l for the Kattegat, the ERGOM and GPBoost models indicate an area of only 2 % (Table 1).

Finally, based on those results, overlay maps were created showing the consistency in the predicted areal extent of oxygen deficiency for three different oxygen thresholds (Fig. 6). With high confidence historic hypoxia occurred over an area of 23 km² in the Belt Sea and with medium confidence that this area reached 56 km², corresponding to less than 1 % of the area. With medium confidence, first signs of hypoxia were also present in the Kiel Bay (1 km²), which is supported by observations (Fig. S1). Oxygen deficiency below 4 mg/l occurred with high and medium confidence in the Belt Sea (636 and 868 km²), the Kiel Bay (398 and 571 km²) and the Bay of Mecklenburg (217 and 856 km², respectively), corresponding to a total area of 2 % to 4 % (Table 2). Finally, oxygen deficiency areas <6 mg/l were predicted in all sub-basins, covering 11 % (high) to 21 % (medium confidence) of the total area (Table 2).

4. Discussion

4.1. Historic hypoxia and oxygen deficiency in the western Baltic Sea

According to our results seasonal hypoxia (oxygen levels <2 mg/l) was not a common feature in the western Baltic Sea around the 1950s and 1960s, with only an area of <1 % in the Belt Sea being predicted with high confidence (Fig. 6, Table 2). With a low degree of confidence, other areas were affected by hypoxia. For example for the Kiel Bay, our estimated hypoxic area with low confidence (3 %) is within the range of an estimate of 0.3–4.9 % based on quantile regression forest methods utilizing annual oxygen minima values (Friedland et al., 2023). According to their results, the Bay of Mecklenburg could have a similar area share of hypoxia as compared to its neighboring western sub-basins (0.1–2.0 %) whereas our low confidence estimate of a 15 % hypoxic area seems to be too large. Our observations, supported by Friedland et al. (2023), suggest that small areas from the Belt Sea to the Arkona Basin may have experienced occasional hypoxia even before 1970 (Fig. S1;

Vock et al., 2023; Piehl et al., 2025). This is further supported by the findings of other studies and reports, which suggest that hypoxia has been observed in the Belt Sea, Kiel Bay, the Bay of Mecklenburg and the Arkona Basin since at least the 1960s, although some evidence is derived from investigations of macrofauna die-offs or fish kills (Diaz et al., 2011; Gerlach, 1990). In contrast, for the Kattegat and the Sound neither the models, nor the observations indicated hypoxia areas. This may be due to the closer proximity to the North Sea, which could be related to the shorter residence time of bottom water in these areas (Bendtsen et al., 2009).

In contrast to hypoxia, oxygen deficiency with concentrations below 6 mg/l was a common feature in the 1960s, with a share of 11 % to 37 % of the area (Fig. 6, Table 2). The smaller share of oxygen deficiency areas predicted in the Belt Sea in comparison to its neighboring eastern sub-basin Kiel Bay (Table 2) can be attributed to the highly dynamic flow conditions that prevail in this region, especially in the Great Belt, which results in more effective mixing. While our methods agree in these areas, there are significant discrepancies in the extent of oxygen deficiency areas below 6 mg/l in the Kattegat, where the GAM predictions are much larger. The presence of neighboring straits and shallow bottom areas in the Belt Sea and the Sound results in reduced bottom water circulation in the southern Kattegat. Besides, the saline Skagerrak water contains elevated levels of nutrients, rendering this area susceptible to seasonal oxygen deficiency during the late summer and autumn months (Rosenberg et al., 2002; Rydberg et al., 2006). In this instance, the area of 3 % with medium confidence could be a more accurate estimate (Table 2). Additionally, remarkable differences in the results of the oxygen deficiency areas were obtained for the Bay of Mecklenburg. Here, ERGOM's prediction indicated significantly larger areas with oxygen levels below 4 mg/l (Fig. 3, Table 1). The oxygen deficiency area below 4 mg/l calculated with a high confidence of 5 % appears to be too low, taking into account that the sub-basin is comparable to Kiel Bay with respect to hydrodynamic and morphological features (Fig. 1) and that receiving salty bottom waters are already depleted in oxygen. In this instance, the average of the high and medium confidence values (11.5 %) could be a more accurate estimate.

The eastern-most located Arkona Basin exhibited no areas below 4 mg/l with high to medium confidence. In contrast, Friedland et al. (2023) predicted an area between 9.1 % and 10.3 % and according to our ERGOM model results, they were almost twice as large (20 %;

Fig. 6. Consistency of oxygen deficiency areas in the historic period (1949–1969) estimated from the statistic, the mechanistic, and the machine-learning models. High confidence shows areas where all three approaches agree, medium confidence show areas where two approaches agree, and low confidence indicates areas supported by one model only.

Table 2

Historical oxygen deficiency areas in square kilometers (percentage share for each sub-basin in parentheses) based on overlapping areas. High confidence is given to areas where all three models predict oxygen deficiency, medium confidence where at least two model predict oxygen deficiency, and low confidence where only one model predicts oxygen deficiency.

Oxygen threshold	Confidence	Kattegat	Belt Sea	The Sound	Kiel Bay	Bay of Mecklenburg	Arkona Basin	Total area
<2 mg/l	High	0 (0)	23 (<1)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	23 (<1)
	Medium	0 (0)	56 (<1)	0 (0)	1 (<1)	0 (0)	0 (0)	57 (<1)
	Low	0 (0)	391 (4)	0 (0)	92 (3)	719 (15)	620 (3)	1822 (3)
<4 mg/l	High	0 (0)	636 (6)	0 (0)	398 (11)	217 (5)	0 (0)	1251 (2)
	Medium	0 (0)	868 (8)	0 (0)	571 (16)	856 (18)	0 (0)	2295 (4)
	Low	0 (0)	1516 (14)	45 (5)	880 (24)	1918 (41)	3473 (20)	7832 (13)
<6 mg/l	High	140 (<1)	1643 (16)	72 (8)	1731 (48)	2104 (45)	1246 (7)	6936 (11)
	Medium	604 (3)	3099 (29)	141 (15)	2386 (66)	2404 (52)	4464 (25)	13,098 (21)
	Low	6266 (26)	4601 (43)	271 (29)	2665 (74)	3016 (65)	5988 (34)	22,808 (37)

Table 1). Given the high RMSE for this particular sub-basin (Table S1) the area prediction by the ERGOM model is too large. Nevertheless, according to the observations there is a probability that small bottom areas with oxygen levels below 4 mg/l were already present in this sub-basin (Piehl et al., 2025). The distinct influges of bottom water over the Drogden and Darss sills result in the formation of discrete bottom water plumes (Lass and Mohrholz, 2003). This means that minimum oxygen concentrations within a profile are not necessarily observed at the greatest depth, which presents a challenge to the efficacy of all currently applied methods. Other machine learning algorithms, such as convolutional neural networks (Kirkwood et al., 2022; Lu et al., 2025; Sunderhaft et al., 2024), are promising and could be tested in the future to assess which machine learning algorithms perform better in reconstruction of sparse spatial data sets.

However, based on our findings and the existing literature on the subject (e.g., Diaz et al., 2011; Friedland et al., 2023), it can be concluded that seasonal oxygen deficiency below 6 mg/l had already become evident in substantial areas of the southwestern Belt Sea, the Kiel Bay, and the Bay of Mecklenburg, with smaller areas affected by levels below 4 mg/l. Furthermore, there is a reasonable likelihood that small areas of oxygen deficiency below 6 mg/l in the remaining sub-basins were present, with the Arkona Basin probably exhibiting minor areas below 4 mg/l (Fig. 6, Fig. S1, Vock et al., 2023).

4.2. Oxygen dynamics in the bottom boundary layer (BBL)

The most significant uncertainty identified relates to the estimation of oxygen concentrations in the bottom boundary layer. Here we define the BBL as the water column within one meter of the seafloor, approximating the definition of the logarithmic layer (Dade et al., 2001; Martens et al., 2016). Our approaches differ in how they consider the BBL, which influences the prediction of near-bottom oxygen deficiency areas. One key difference between the GAM/GPBoost and the ERGOM model is that the GAM/GPBoost models use oxygen measurements as the basis for area estimates of near-bottom hypoxia and oxygen deficiency. A limitation is that oxygen concentrations within the water layer one meter above the seafloor are hardly recorded (Fredriksson et al., 2024). Even though the GAM model accounts for the relationship of oxygen with depth, it is questionable whether and to what extent the oxygen gradients in the BBL are reflected in the results, since historic measurements were also mainly taken outside of the BBL (Piehl et al., 2025). In addition, the GPBoost model utilizes measurements up to five meter above the seafloor and thus may likewise fail to accurately reflect the steep oxygen gradients of the BBL. In the ERGOM model, a sediment layer is included, and the oxygen dynamics in the bottom water layer are influenced by oxygen-consuming processes in the sediment layer, i.e., mineralization of detritus (Neumann et al., 2022). This means that the steep oxygen gradients of the BBL are better reflected in the lowermost model layer utilized for assessing near-bottom oxygen deficiency. Nevertheless, the parameterization focused on the central Baltic Sea with permanent hypoxia and the more dynamic bottom processes of the

western Baltic Sea are likely not represented optimally. Due to the absence of oxygen data in the lowest few centimeters of the water column in our study area for validation, the reliability of ERGOM in reflecting the BBL remains uncertain.

In general, the bottom water is often characterized by several sub-layers (Trowbridge and Lentz, 2018), exhibiting high spatial and temporal dynamics in our study area (Stips et al., 1998). Stips et al. (1998) investigated the bottom water in the Bay of Mecklenburg and Arkona Basin. According to their definition the BBL includes a homogenous layer about 2.2 m thick, overlaying a logarithmic layer on average 0.9 m thick (the BBL according to our definition), and an about two centimeter thick viscous sublayer. They found that the mean temporal and spatial variability of the homogenous layer is approximately 23 cm/h and 64 cm/km, respectively (Stips et al., 1998), which highlights the challenge in measuring the BBL and its oxygen dynamics.

Previous studies in the western Baltic Sea have already discussed the lack of information from measurements in the BBL and the resulting possible underestimation of hypoxia (Conley et al., 2002). That low oxygen concentrations can be restricted to the BBL has been shown for the Northern Gulf of Mexico, where upper limits of hypoxic waters coincide with that of the BBL (Fennel and Testa, 2019). Holtappels and Lorke (2011) estimated increased oxygen gradients in the benthic boundary layer in a German lake system for low current velocities and stratified shear flow, concluding that hypoxic conditions in the bottom water of lakes and the coastal ocean may occur in the first tens of centimeters above the sediment. A recent study by Fredriksson et al. (2024) investigated oxygen concentrations in a ~50 cm thick water layer above the bottom on Sweden's east coast. They discovered that hypoxia often occurs over a period of a few hours to several days, which was not previously detected by operational monitoring programs that usually sample one meter above the seafloor. From this they conclude that hypoxia and anoxia probably occur more frequently in these near-bottom water layers than previously assumed.

In view of this information, it is very likely that the observed historical oxygen concentrations do not reflect the situation in the BBL either. From a management perspective, however, it is crucial for an oxygen indicator that the target values and the status assessment are consistent. Hence, if the oxygen status is based on interpolating measurements that do not include the steep gradient of the BBL, as it is currently the case, then the approach for setting area targets should also not do so. In order to develop a more relevant indicator for the benthic fauna, it is recommended to incorporate the BBL into the indicator assessment and the target setting approach in the future.

4.3. Implications for indicator development

Presumably, due to limited measurement data in historical periods, alternative approaches to derive target values for oxygen deficiency were utilized in other areas experiencing oxygen deficiency. In the Gulf of Mexico for example, coastal hypoxia was only mapped systematically since 1985 and historical occurrence of hypoxia was mainly assessed

through sediment records (Rabalais et al., 2007). Thus, the area target of 5000 km² was derived from research on nutrient load reduction scenarios and a pragmatic decision balancing ecological restoration and economic and social considerations (Mississippi River/Gulf of Mexico Watershed Nutrient Task Force, 2001; U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, 2007). Neither for the Chesapeake Bay, the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA) derived area thresholds defining a ‘good status’ based on historical area estimates (Hagy et al., 2004). Instead, the USEPA established water quality standards (WQS) for dissolved oxygen, e.g., a year-round threshold of a 7-day mean ≥ 4 mg/l for open-water (Tango and Batiuk, 2013). The WQS are specific for various aquatic environments, thereby reflecting the seasonal composition of the water column and the habitat requirements of diverse aquatic organisms (Zhang et al., 2024; U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, 2003a). Assessment results are evaluated against biologically-based reference data, i.e., data taken from laboratory or empirical field data from areas known to be unimpaired by the stressor but including natural variability (U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, 2003b). A significant benefit of this approach is that, besides including the intensity and spatial dimension, it considers the temporal dimensions, with the WQS selected based on the hypoxia tolerance of key organisms. Acknowledging the differing sensitivities to oxygen concentrations by various organism (Vaquer-Sunyer and Duarte, 2008) we also analyzed different oxygen thresholds. Adopting threshold values that reflect habitat requirements and seasonal dynamics of habitats in the Baltic Sea would be an important step towards biologically meaningful indicators. However, the derivation of such metrics for the Baltic Sea may be much more complex than for the Chesapeake Bay. The brackish character of the Baltic Sea leads to strong gradients in biodiversity, from marine species in the entrance area of the Baltic Sea to freshwater species which increase towards the north-east (Snoeijjs-Leijonmalm et al., 2017). Moreover, species that exhibit ecological and/or economic relevance in one region may lack equivalent importance in another (e.g., commercial fish species; Rosciszewski-Dodgson and Cirella, 2024). These factors need to be considered in future research efforts to derive biologically relevant targets for oxygen indicators.

Considering the target setting approach, i.e., utilizing a historical oxygen or a biological reference, both are valid (HELCOM, 2013; Tango and Batiuk, 2013). Since biological references depict a good status from a current period, they can account for climate change-induced changes in hydro-meteorological conditions. This can be a limitation when considering historical references, should the climate change signal be neglected. The historical targets may never be achieved, which would have a negative impact on the motivation of management efforts. Historic references, in comparison to biological references, highlight the degree of degradation and restoration needs, offering concrete environmental goals. For example, in the Baltic Sea, oxygen deficiency is partly a natural phenomenon (Conley et al., 2011) and targets for permanent hypoxia are based on a period that accounts for some degree of human influence (HELCOM, 2013). Thus, a combination of both approaches would be the most balanced strategy, taking into account historical findings while adapting to current and future ecological conditions.

A good way forward for the Baltic Sea would be to consider the habitat requirements for high biodiversity, but also the seasonal oxygen demand, e.g., depending on different life stages of vulnerable species (setting maximum tolerable time periods for certain thresholds). In order to subsequently establish specific targets, we recommend that historical area estimates are then combined with the designated time thresholds.

5. Conclusion

Although seasonal hypoxia (oxygen levels <2 mg/l) was not a common feature, it is plausible that smaller areas in the western Baltic Sea were already occasionally affected by such conditions prior to 1970.

While there is a reasonable likelihood for the presence of a notable area with seasonal oxygen deficiency below 6 mg/l in the entrance area (Kattegat), the likelihood is high for all other sub-basins where areas <4 mg/l are also observed. A major uncertainty discovered by the application of our approach relates to the estimation of oxygen concentrations in the bottom boundary layer, as this is estimated differently by our methods and all methods are presently lacking observational data for model tuning. A key benefit of the current approach is that the methods together provide a more robust estimate of the historic situation as well as an estimate of the uncertainty. For the derivation of ecologically relevant target values, i.e., target values that allow for high biodiversity, it would be important to link historically derived target values of oxygen deficiency areas with biological-derived target values, e.g., by including time-exposure thresholds derived from biological references.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Sarah Piehl: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Jacob Carstensen:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Thomas Neumann:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Clarissa Vock:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the author SP used DeepL Write (<https://www.deepl.com/de/write>) for some passages in the text in order to improve the readability. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2025.118464>.

Data availability

Data has been archived within the Zenodo repository: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15211657>.

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